

A Tertiary Care Hospital's Clinical Profile and Prognosis for Severe Dengue Infection in Children

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Abstract:

Aim: The aim of the present study was to evaluate the typical clinical presentation, biochemical findings, and prognosis of severe dengue fever.

Materials and Methods: This study was conducted at the Pediatrics Department of Krishna Mohan Medical College and Hospital, Pali Dungra, Sonkh Road, Mathura, Uttar Pradesh, India. Of all the dengue cases, 60 were deemed serious. Only adolescents (10-19) were considered for the study.

Results: Among the 60 severe dengue cases, 53.3% (n=32) had Dengue shock syndrome (DSS), 18.3% (n=11) had Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever (DHF), and 11.6% (n=7) had Expanded Dengue Syndrome (EDS). After being admitted to the hospital, 13.3% (n=8) of the patients with DSS developed DHF, and 3.3% (n=2) of those with DHF developed grade EDS. The most common blood type among patients was B+, accounting for 38.3% (n=23), followed by O+ at 35% (n=21), A+ at 23.3% (n=14), and AB+ at 3.3% (n=2). Fever was the most observed symptom, lasting 4-6 days in 55.9% (n=33) of cases, followed by ≤ 3 days in 38.3% (n=23) cases and ≥ 7 days in 5% (n=3) cases. Abdominal pain and vomiting were observed in 76.6% (n=46) of patients, and shock was observed in 61.6% (n=37) of patients. Shock was observed in 60% (n=36) of patients, pleural effusion in 45% (n=27), ascites in 33.3% (n=20), and hepatomegaly in 20% (n=12) cases. Rash was observed in 18.3% (n=11) of patients, while loose motions and difficulty breathing were observed in 15% (n=9) of cases each. Headache was present in 10% (n=6) of cases, and myalgia and arthralgia were observed in 8.3% (n=5) of cases. Convulsion and altered consciousness were rare presentations seen in 6.6% (n=4) of cases and 5% (n=3) of cases, respectively.

Conclusion: Severe dengue is characterized by nausea, vomiting, shock, ascites, and pleural effusion. Important findings in patients with severe disease include elevated AST and D-dimer levels, low fibrinogen and albumin levels, and hyponatremia. With prompt diagnosis and appropriate treatment, its severity can be reduced.

Keywords: Dengue fever, Aspartate Transaminase, Fibrinogen, Pleural Effusion, Shock, Albumin.

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Introduction

Dengue fever is a leading viral disease spread by mosquitoes. It infects annually as many as 400 million people causing 40,000 deaths owing to severe cases [1]. The ideas of vector control have formed the basis of dengue prevention and control efforts [1]. To effectively manage and prevent poor consequences, it is necessary to understand the clinical profile and prognosis of severe dengue infection in children [2,3]. Clinical symptoms of acute dengue infection in children might range from shock-inducing plasma leakage to severe bleeding and organ damage [3]. Dengue shock syndrome (DSS) is the most severe form of dengue,

according to the World Health Organization (WHO) [4]. In children, acute dengue can cause a rapid escalation of symptoms including high fever, headache, retro-orbital pain, myalgia, arthralgia, and rash [5]. Mucosal hemorrhage, hepatomegaly, and indications of circulatory collapse are symptoms that become apparent as the disease advances. Thrombocytopenia, hemoconcentration, increased liver enzymes, and, under extreme circumstances, disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC) are common results found in laboratory testing [6]. The outcome of a severe dengue infection in a kid depends on how quickly

the symptoms are identified, how quickly treatment begins, and what measures are put in place to control the illness [7]. Rapid worsening and deadly results can result from poor medical care or a delayed diagnosis. Important aspects of treatment include administering fluids quickly to stop plasma loss, keeping a close eye on symptoms of shock and providing transfusion support in cases of severe bleeding [8]. Organ failure, especially dysfunction of the liver and kidneys, requires careful monitoring for potential consequences. Most children with severe dengue infection can make a full recovery with the best medical care [9]. Nevertheless, it is crucial to undergo thorough follow-up care because a portion of patients may endure a prolonged sickness or acquire long-term problems [10]. The rapid progression and catastrophic outcomes of severe dengue infection provide substantial concerns in pediatric healthcare. Healthcare practitioners must have a comprehensive knowledge of the clinical features and prognosis of severe dengue infection in children to reduce morbidity and mortality caused by this potentially fatal condition through the implementation of effective therapies in a timely manner [11].

Several novel dengue vaccines are, nevertheless, under research and development at this time. Dengvaxia, the first dengue vaccine, was registered in December 2015 and is already licensed in other countries, including Mexico and the Philippines [12]. Dengue immunization should only be administered to children in high-burden countries who are nine years old or older, according to a 2016 position document by the World Health Organization (WHO). Hence the aim of the present study was to evaluate the typical clinical presentation, biochemical findings, and prognosis of severe dengue fever.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted at the Pediatrics Department of Krishna Mohan Medical College and Hospital, Pali Dungra, Sonkh Road, Mathura, Uttar Pradesh, India. Of all the dengue cases, 60 were deemed serious. The duration of the study was between August 2022 to December 2023.

Inclusion criteria: Children within a defined age range, typically ranging from 10 to 19, are included in the study. Participants with laboratory-confirmed dengue infection through NS1 antigen, IgM antibody, or RT-PCR test, and who also had severe dengue illness were included. Children meeting predefined criteria for severe dengue infection are included in the study. This may include WHO guidelines for the classification of severe dengue, such as DHF or DSS. Participants exhibited characteristic clinical manifestations of severe dengue infection, including high fever, severe

headache, retro-orbital pain, myalgia, arthralgia, rash, mucosal bleeding, hepatomegaly, and signs of circulatory collapse. Informed Consent: Informed consent was obtained from parents or legal guardians of the participating children. Ethical considerations regarding participant autonomy and welfare are taken care of in the present study population.

Exclusion Criteria: Children outside the defined age range set for the study were excluded. Participants with negative laboratory-confirmed dengue infection through NS1 antigen, IgM antibody, or RT-PCR test, and who also had severe dengue illness were excluded. Children with alternative diagnoses that could mimic severe dengue infection or affect the interpretation of study outcomes including acute febrile illnesses such as malaria, bacterial sepsis, or viral infections like influenza were excluded. Pre-existing Conditions and individuals with chronic diseases such as diabetes mellitus, immunodeficiency disorders, or underlying hematological disorders were excluded. Children who have received recent blood transfusions were excluded from the study to avoid confounding factors related to changes in hematological parameters and immune response. Children with incomplete medical records or insufficient documentation of dengue diagnosis, severity criteria, or clinical outcomes were excluded to ensure data reliability and accuracy. Participants or their legal guardians who withdrew consent during the course of the study were excluded from further analysis to uphold ethical principles of voluntary participation and respect for participant autonomy.

Statistical Analysis: In situations where there were two separate groups with normally distributed data, quantitative variables were analyzed using an independent t-test. The qualitative data was analyzed using the Chi-square test for differences between proportions for inferential purposes, with independent variables. A p-value less than 0.05 was considered significant.

Results

The overall number of severe dengue cases was 60. An average age of 11.23 ± 3.86 years was recorded for the study cohort of 10 years (minimum) to 19 years (maximum). 31.6 % of the study population ranged between the ages of 12 and 15 and the rest 68.3 % were either below 12 years or above 15 years of age. Half of the patients (51 %) were found to have maintained a normal weight, while 26.4% were obese, 19.8% were overweight, and 2.8% were underweight. The hospital stay duration ranged from 1 to 14 days, with an average of 5.9 ± 3 days for all the recruited study population, out of which 60 % (n=36) of patients spent three days or less in the intensive care unit.

Out of 60 severe dengue cases, 53.3% (n=32) had DSS, 18.3 % (n= 11) had DHF, and 11.6 % (n=7) had Expanded Dengue Syndrome (EDS). After admission and hospitalization, 13.3 % (n=8) of patients with DSS developed DHF, while 3.3 % (n=2) of patients with DHF developed grade EDS. A total of 38.3 % (n=23) of patients had the B+ blood type, 35 % (n=21) had the O+ type, 23.3 % (n=14) had the A+ type, and 3.4 % (n=2) had the AB+ type. The duration of fever was 4-6 days in 55.9 % (n=33) patients, ≤ 3 days in 38.3 % (n=23) cases and ≥ 7 days in 5 % (n=3) cases. The next most common symptom observed was abdominal pain and vomiting in 76.6 % (n=46) patients followed by shock in 61.6 % (n=37) patients. Shock was observed in 53.3 % (n=32) patients, pleural effusion was seen in 45 % (n=27) patients, ascites was seen in 33.3 % (n=20) patients, and hepatomegaly was seen in 20 % (n=12) cases. Rash was observed in 18.3 % (n=11) patients, loose motions was observed in 15 % (n=9) cases, difficulty in breathing was observed in 15 % (n=9) cases, and cough in 8.3 (n=5) cases. Headache was present in 10 % (n=6) cases, myalgia and arthralgia in 8.3 % (n=5) cases, convulsion and altered consciousness were rare presentations seen in 6.6% (n=4) cases and 5% (n=3) cases respectively.

The bleeding manifestation was seen in 21.6 % (n=13) of patients. The most common bleeding manifestation was hematemesis and melena in 16.6 % (n=10) cases followed by prick site bleeding in 3.3 % (n=2) cases, gum bleeding in 1.6 % (n=1) cases, and menorrhagia in 1.6% (n=1) case. 46 patients in our study were positive for NS1. The next most common types of positivity were IgM (17 cases), RT-PCR (12 cases), IgG and IgM (8 patients), NSI and RT-PCR (12 patients), and NSI and IgM (5 cases). Out of all the liver enzymes, AST or SGOT was higher in 36 patients, while ALT or SGPT was higher in 26 patients. In 21 cases, the prothrombin time and the activated partial thromboplastin time were both longer than they should have been. In 42 patients, the D-dimer level was high, and in 18 patients, it was low. These levels indicate the severity of dengue fever i.e., DHF and DSS. In ten cases, the creatinine level was high. Hyponatremia was observed in 28 cases adolescents in our study and was the most common electrolyte abnormality. Other electrolyte abnormalities observed were hypokalemia in 11 cases, hyperkalemia in 3 cases and hypernatremia in 3 cases. These levels were an indication of how severe dengue was, like DHF.

Discussion

Laboratory parameters and clinical manifestations of severe dengue fever exhibit considerable variation. We anticipate that by identifying the frequency, signs, and symptoms of abnormal laboratory results, we can enhance our capacity to

predict and manage cases in a timely and effective manner. The overall number of severe dengue cases was 60. An average age of 6.67 ± 4.68 years was recorded for the study cohort of 10 years (minimum) to 19 years (maximum). 31.8 % of the study population ranged between the ages of 12 and 15 and the rest 68.2 % were between below 12 years and above 15 years of age. The hospital stay duration ranged from 1 to 14 days, with an average of 5.9 ± 3 days for all the recruited study population, out of which 60 % (n=36) of patients spent three days or less in the intensive care unit. Out of 60 severe dengue cases, 53.3% (n=32) had DSS, 18.3 % (n= 11) had DHF, and 11.6 % (n=7) had Expanded Dengue Syndrome (EDS). After admission and hospitalization, 13.3 % (n=8) of patients with DSS developed DHF, while 3.3 % (n=2) of patients with DHF developed EDS. Results commensurate with those reported by prior study [6] were evident in the severe dengue patient cohort. These patients exhibited the most severe vascular leakage, followed by severe hemorrhaging and then severe organ dysfunction [6]. Among the 266 patients who required intensive care unit (ICU) treatment, 216 individuals experienced an average ICU stay of less than three days [6]. In contrast, a study found that hospital stay lasted between three and six days [7]. Consistent with prior research, in the current investigation, 55.9% (n=33) of patients displayed fever with a duration of 4-6 days [7], while 38.9% (n=23) had fever for ≤ 3 days [6], and 5.2% (n=3) experienced fever for ≥ 7 days. The present study found that fever was the most common clinical manifestation, affecting 59 patients, which is consistent with previous reports. In two separate studies, fever was reported in 94.6% and 96.8% of patients, respectively [8,9].

The next most common symptom observed was abdominal pain and vomiting in 76.6 % (n=46) patients followed by shock in 61.6 % (n=37) patients. Shock was observed in 60 % (n=36) patients, pleural effusion was seen in 45 % (n=27) patients, ascites was seen in 33.3 % (n=20) patients, and hepatomegaly was seen in 20 % (n=12) cases. Rash was observed in 18.3 % (n=11) patients, loose motions was observed in 15 % (n=9) cases, difficulty in breathing was observed in 15 % (n=9) cases, and cough in 8.3 (n=5) cases. Headache was present in 10 % (n=6) cases, myalgia and arthralgia in 8.3 % (n=5) cases, convulsion and altered consciousness were rare presentations seen in 6.6% (n=4) cases and 5% (n=3) cases respectively. The bleeding manifestation was seen in 21.6 % (n=13) of patients. The most common bleeding manifestation was hematemesis and melena in 16.6 % (n=10) cases followed by prick site bleeding in 3.3 % (n=2) cases, gum bleeding in 1.6 % (n=1) cases, and menorrhagia in 1.6% (n=1) cases. Shock was identified in 70.8% of patients [10]. Hematemesis and melena were the most frequent manifesta-

tions of bleeding, occurring in 19 cases. This finding is consistent with the research conducted by [11,12]. In contrast, studies showed hepatomegaly was the most prevalent physical finding in studies [6-9]. It was demonstrated that AST was elevated in a greater proportion than ALT. This finding was consistent with the results of another study in which AST was elevated. In our present study, we observed lower albumin levels in 47 (78 %) cases out of study population of 60 cases. This was almost the same as the value (44 cases) found by which was one of the indicators of seriousness [2-4]. In one study a low albumin level was detected in 59 cases, which was nearly like what was reported by [1] but significantly greater which was reported by [2,3]. Out of 60 cases, of the 28 cases (47.8%), hyponatremia was identified as the most prevalent electrolyte imbalance. In 42 cases (71.8%), the coagulation profile showed an elevated D-dimer (DD) level, whereas in 34 cases (57.0%), the coagulation profile showed a low fibrinogen level. The results showed a longer activated partial thromboplastin time (aPTT) in 38.4% of patients. Out of 28 cases, five percent of these cases were fatal. These levels were an indication of how severe dengue was, like DHF. In ten cases, the creatine level was high. A positive correlation was also observed between DD and the severity of dengue across all stages of the disease, including febrile, toxic, and convalescent (P value <0.05).

Conclusion

A terrifying disease that affects youngsters is severe dengue fever. The case fatality rate can be considerably reduced with quick diagnosis and management, regardless of the presentation or features. Following the most recent national recommendations, our study details the most common and uncommon symptoms, how to grade their severity, what tests to do, and how to manage them. Common symptoms in severe cases include nausea, vomiting, shock, ascites, and pleural effusion. Hyponatremia, low fibrinogen and albumin levels, and elevated AST and D-dimer levels are noteworthy laboratory results. Reducing the impact of the condition requires prompt diagnosis and effective treatment.

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